

A STUDY ON THE EXPORT PERFORMANCE OF COTTON YARN IN SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE

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Abstract:

The cotton industry in India traditionally, after agriculture, is the only industry that has generated huge employment for both skilled and unskilled labor in textiles. The cotton industry continues to be the second largest employment generating sector in India. It offers direct employment to over 35 million in the country. The share of textiles in total exports was 11.04% during April–July 2016, as per the Ministry of Textiles. During 20017-2018, Indian cotton industry was decreased 37.5 million bales to 35 million bale 60% of the Indian textile Industry is cotton based. It is the second most developed sector in the Indian Textile industries. It provides employment to huge amount of people but its productions and employment is seasonal depending upon the seasonal nature of the production. Due to the high need and growth of the industry in the world India should keep its pace to compete with its competitors. There should be necessary technology and machinery up gradation on a periodic scale for low-cost and quality products.

Key Words: Employment, Production & Technology

Introduction:

Cotton is a soft, fluffy staple fiber that grows in a bowl, or protective case, around the seeds of the cotton plants of the genus *Gossypium* in the mallow family *Malvaceae*. The fiber is almost pure cellulose. Under natural conditions, the cotton bolls will increase the dispersal of the seeds. Cotton is arguably the world's most important nonfood crop. It supplies about 80 percent of the world's natural fibers and continues to be primary material in half the world's textiles despite competition from synthetic fibers. Cotton is ideal for making cloth because its fibers bond and interlock when spun into long strands that can be easily dyed. Cotton plays an important role in the Indian economy as the country textile industry is predominantly cotton based Indian is one of the largest producers and as well as exporters of the cotton yarn the Indian textile industry contributes 5 percent to country's gross domestic product the industry is also the second largest employer in the country. Cotton is used to make clothes, towels, sheets, rugs, draperies, cloth, batting, cellulose products, cordage, and sewing threads. It can also be ground into currency, crushed into vegetable oil, and woven into coffee filters, book bindings, tents, diapers and fishnet. Fire men like cotton firehouses over polyester ones because they soak up enough water to keep them from melting. Environmentalists like it mops up oil spills better than almost any other material. And doctors like for bandages and sutures because of its durability under a lot of different conditions.

Statement of the Problem:

- ✓ The Textile industry in India traditionally, after agriculture, is the only industry that has generated huge employment for both skilled and unskilled labor in textiles. The study concentrates on the export performance of cotton yarn in the spinning sector.
- ✓ The study extends to know how often the technology is been updated and various government funds that help for it.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study about the position of cotton yarn industry in world market
- ✓ To study about the position of cotton yarn industry in India
- ✓ The study the current scenario of cotton yarn industry in Coimbatore
- ✓ To analyse the export performance of cotton yarn industry in Coimbatore
- ✓ To suggest the measure of improvement

Problems of Cotton Textile Industry in India:

- ✓ Shortage of raw materials - Raw material determines 35 percent of the total production cost the country is short of cotton, particularly long- staple cotton which is imported from Pakistan, Kenya, Uganda, Sudan, Egypt, Tanzania, U.S.A. and Peru. Fluctuating prices and uncertainties in the availability of raw material cause low production and sickness to the mills.
- ✓ Obsolete machinery - In India most of the cotton textile mills are working with old and obsolete machinery. According to one estimate in India over 60 per cent of the spindles are more than 25 years old. Obsolete machinery leads to low output and poor quality of goods.

- ✓ Power shortage - Textile mills are facing acute shortage of power. Supplies of coal are difficult to obtain and frequent cuts in electricity and load shedding affect the industry badly. This leads to loss of man hours, low production and loss in the mills.
- ✓ Low productivity of labor - Low productivity is another major problem of cotton textile industry. On an average an Indian factory worker only handles 380 spindles and 2 looms as compared to 1,500-2,000 spindles and 30 looms in Japan. Strikes, layoffs, retrenchments are the common features of many cotton mills in the country.
- ✓ Competition in foreign markets - The Indian cotton textile goods are facing stiff competition in foreign markets from Taiwan, South Korea and Japan whose goods are cheaper and better in quality.

Limitation of the Study:

- ✓ The study is conducted only in Coimbatore.
- ✓ The study is conducted within a limited period.
- ✓ The study was taken from the manufacturer point of view.
- ✓ Possibility of researcher bias
- ✓ Limited respondents because of shortage of time.
- ✓ The location of the production unit and office were different

Research Methodology:

Research is defined as human activity based on the intellectual application in the investigation of matter. The primary purpose for applied research is discovering, interpreting, and the development of the methods and systems for the advancement of human knowledge on a wide variety of scientific matters of our world and the universe. Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem.

Research Design:

It is a conceptual structure with which research would be conducted. The study was descriptive in nature.

Descriptive Research:

The descriptive research describes attitude, perceptions, characteristics, activities, and situations. This type of research builds off from previous information, shows a relationship between variables, uses representative samples, has a structured research plan, is expensive, and conclusive.

Area of Study:

The study has conducted in the cotton yarn manufacturing industries around Coimbatore.

Sampling Size:

The size of 11 has been chosen for the questionnaire survey on basis of convenience sampling.

Sampling Design:

The procedure by which a particular sample is chosen from a population is known as sampling design. Convenience sampling was adopted for conducting the research work.

Data Collection:

Primary data as well as secondary data was used for data collection.

Primary Data:

The data collected by the researcher himself/herself is referred to a primary data. In this study the primary data were collected from various cotton yarn manufacturing industries around Coimbatore through questionnaire method.

Secondary Data:

The data collected from already existing sources is known as the secondary data. The secondary data for this project was collected from journals and websites.

Construction of Questionnaire:

A questionnaire consists of a number of questions generally with parts such as the demographic variables followed by the main theme.

Scaling Technique Used:

Summated scales (or Likert - type scales) are developed by utilizing the item analysis approach wherein a particular item is evaluated on the basis of how well it discriminates between those persons whose total score is high and those whose score is low. Those items or statements that best meet this sort of discrimination test are included in the final instrument.

Statistical Tools Used:

Percentage analysis and One way ANOVA

Analysis and Interpretation:

Area of Location Wise Distribution of the Respondents:

Area of Location	No of Respondent	Percentage
Rural	2	18.2%
Urban	6	54.5%
Semi Urban	3	27.3%

Total	11	100%
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Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

On the location wise distribution of the respondents 18.2% are from the rural, 54.5% are from the urban and 27.3% from the semi-urban

Year of Operations in Spinning Industry Wise Distribution of the Respondents:

Year of Operation	No of Respondent	Percentage
Less than 10 years	3	27.3%
10-20 years	3	27.3%
20-35 years	3	27.3%
35 years above	2	18.2%
Total	11	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

On the year of operations the respondents 27.3% are from the less than 10 years 27.3% are from the 10-20 years, 27.3% from the 20-35 years and 18.2% from the 35 years above.

Major Product Wise Distribution of the Respondents:

Major Product	No of Respondent	Percentage
Cotton yarn	7	63.6%
Nylon yarn	2	18.2%
Wool	-	-
Others	2	18.2%
Total	11	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

On the major product is the respondents 63.6% are using cotton yarn 18.2% are using nylon yarn wool have 0% and others are using 18.2%

ANOVA:

H0: there is no Association between frequency of upgrade and high quality of garments.

ANOVA Table 1					
	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.977	3	.659	6.152	.023
Within Groups	.750	7	.107		
Total	2.727	10			

Interpretation:

$v_1=3$ $v_2=7$, Calculated value $f = 6.152$, $v_1=3$, $v_2=7$ table value $F=4.35$, there is association between upgrade and high quality of garments

H0: there is no Association between kind of technology and increased finished products.

ANOVA Table 2					
	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.836	3	.612	1.128	.401
Within Groups	3.800	7	.543		
Total	5.636	10			

Interpretation:

$v_1=3$ $v_2=7$, calculated value $f = 5.636$, $v_1=3$, $v_2=7$ table value $F=4.35$, there is a association between kind of technology and increased in finished products

H0: there is a Association between frequency and wastage of raw material.

ANOVA Table 3					
	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.594	1	.594	2.506	.148
Within Groups	2.133	9	.237		
Total	2.727	10			

Interpretation:

$v_1=3$ $v_2=7$, calculated value $f = 2.727$, $v_1=3$, $v_2=7$, table value $F=4.35$, there is a association between kind of technology and increased in finished products

H0: there is no Association between value addition to attract more buyers and frequency of up gradation and R and D.

ANOVA Table 4					
	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.

Between Groups	6.200	3	2.067	8.037	.011
Within Groups	1.800	7	.257		
Total	8.000	10			

Interpretation:

$v_1=3$ $v_2=7$, calculated value $f = 8.000$, $v_1=3$, $v_2=7$ table value $F=4.35$, there is a association between value addition to attract more buyers and frequency of up gradation and R and D.

HO: there is a no Association between technology upgrade would improve labour efficiency and GDP growth.

ANOVA Table 5					
	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.500	3	.500	.538	.671
Within Groups	6.500	7	.929		
Total	8.000	10			

Interpretation:

$v_1=3$ $v_2=7$, calculated value $f = 8.000$, $v_1=3$, $v_2=7$ table value $F=4.35$, There is an association between upgrade would improve labor efficiency and GDP growth.

Findings:

Demographic Profile:

- ✓ The result show that the maximum 54.5% respondents have their unit in Urban area
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 27.3% respondents are in the spinning industry for over 35 years
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 63.6% respondents produce Cotton Yarn as their major product
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 54.5% respondents suggest European Countries as their target market
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 45.5% respondents produce <2000 m.ton as a total capacity of production
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 45.5% respondents prefer Chennai and Kochi for port operations
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 54.5% respondents use CFS as a customs procedure for export of goods
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 45.5% respondents have both fully automatic and semi-automatic technology
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 63.6% respondents update their machinery regularly
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 54.5% respondents update their technology 10-15 years once.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 63.6% respondents suggest the ISO certification.

ANOVA:

There is association between upgrade and high quality of garments

- ✓ There is an association between kind of technology and increased in finished products
- ✓ There is an association between value addition to attract more buyers and frequency of up gradation and R and D.
- ✓ There is an association between upgrade would improve labor efficiency and GDP growth

Suggestions:

- ✓ The globalization and liberalization has brought out a period of competence. So the export should be enhanced to compete with globalization.
- ✓ There should be a periodic up gradation in the technology for the spinning sector
- ✓ More improved cultivation method can be used for the production of cotton.
- ✓ The GDP would grow if there are efficient growth in technology in the spinning sector
- ✓ More waste management and dying machinery should be installed.
- ✓ Government policies have been laid for the improvement of cotton industry in India.

Conclusion:

The cotton industry in India traditionally, after agriculture, is the only industry that has generated huge employment for both skilled and unskilled labor in textiles. The cotton industry continues to be the second largest employment generating sector in India. It offers direct employment to over 35 million in the country. The share of textiles in total exports was 11.04% during April–July 2016, as per the Ministry of Textiles. During 20017-2018, Indian cotton industry was decreased 37.5 million bales to 35 million bale 60% of the Indian textile Industry is cotton based. It is the second most developed sector in the Indian Textile industries. It provides employment to huge amount of people but its productions and employment is seasonal depending upon the seasonal nature of the production. Due to the high need and growth of the industry in the world India should keep its pace to compete with its competitors. There should be necessary technology and machinery up gradation on a periodic scale for low-cost and quality products.

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